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A FRAMEWORK FOR INTEGRATED DATABASE OF NTFP FOR SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOOD OF TRIBAL'S

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Abstract

Forest benefits one and all by its intangible services and goods. Timber and non-timber forest produce are the main product of forest. Timber produce is well managed and documented by forest department. Non timber forest products (NTFPs) are mainly dependent on tribals for collection and sales. Nationalized NTFP's are well regulated by the government, providing better return to NTFP's collectors, but non-nationalized NTFP's fetch lesser return and volatility of income is high as their number forms major part of the collection. Lack of documentation or database and non-integration of information about produce led them to slip in the hands of middlemen who purchase at much lesser price. NTFP's as a Non-timber forest produce play an important role in sustainable livelihood and poverty alleviation of tribal's. These make up to 80% contribution to the income of forest dependent tribal's. This paper discusses the framework for an integrated

database for nationalized and non-nationalized NTFP's which could help in pricing, conservation, forecasting and commercialization. Further this could lead to socio-economic development and women empowerment of forest dependant tribal's.

Key Word: Non timber forest products (NTFP), Poverty alleviation, sustainable livelihood, Commercialization..

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Introduction:

In past decade an enormous growth of interest in non-timber forest products (NTFPs) among conservation and development organisations has been observed. Numerous reasons are there for the general spread and sudden rise in global interest in NTFPs. It is estimated that around 80 percent of the population of the developing world use non-timber forest products (NTFP) for health and nutritional needs. It is believed that the promotion of sustainable use of NTFPs could lead to a win-win situation for poverty alleviation and bio-diversity conservation. This is due to the increasing recognition that NTFPs can contribute significantly to the livelihoods of tribal and communities' dependant on forests.

NTFPs are known by its various names like Minor Forest Produce (MFP), Laghu Van Upaj (LVU), and Non-Wood Forest Produce (NWFP).

The term NTFP was coined by de Beer and Mcdermott in 1989, they define NTFP as "The term Non timber forest products (NTFPs) encompasses all biological materials other than timber, which extracted from forest for human use."

1. UN-FAO define NTFP- " a product of biological origin other than wood derived from forests, other wooded land and trees outside forests that may be gathered from the wild or produced in forest plantations, agro-forestry schemes & from trees outside forests".
2. Peters (1996) define- NTFPs are a collection of biological resources derived from both natural & managed forests & other wooded areas".
3. The scheduled tribe and other traditional forest dwellers act 2006 define "minor forest produce includes all non-timber forest produce of plant origin including bamboo, brushwood, stumps, cane , tussar, cocoons, wax, lac tendu or kendu leaves medicinal plants and herbs, roots , tubers and the like;"

Non-Timber Forest Products (NTFPs) abundantly available in various ecological domains across India have been identified to serve critical living

needs of the communities. The multiplicity in using NTFPs and their importance in reaching subsistence as well as income generation necessities have now been increasingly recognized for reducing the poverty of rural and vulnerable communities.

More than 6 million peoples who living in India is forest dwellers. They don't have any option to survive in this world without forest due to those reasons; they used to cut the forest for their food as well as shelter purpose. According to the government rules and order as well as environment safety concern, they should not cut the forest without any reason. Before the terminology called NTFPs came to existing in India, peoples were struggled too much especially forest dwellers.

After the terminology called NTFPs came to exist among the people, the poverty level of the people reduced gradually. They have understood the value of the forest as well as the profit comes out from the NTFPs, NTFPs could reduce the poverty level of rural and vulnerable communities through following ways;

- I. Providing employment opportunities for unemployed men and women through harvesting of the NTFPs products.
- II. Increasing the forest cover area by conserving the trees from forest dwellers through offering the sustainable livelihood status through NTFPs opportunities.
- III. Poverty alleviation is the main focus of NTFPs concept that to focus on vulnerable communities through SHGs, NGOs and cooperatives.
- IV. NTFPs could maintain the equilibrium level between rural communities and forest, through these equilibrium NTFPs could reduce the poverty level among the rural and vulnerable communities.

A large number of valuable medicinal plants naturally wing mostly in fragile ecosystems that are predominantly inhabited by rural poor and indigenous communities. The sustainable management of these traditionally used plants

not only help conserve nationally and globally important biodiversity but also provide critical resources to sustain livelihoods.

The medicinal plant resources found all over the world are important because nearly 75% of the world's population uses them. Of all the known plant species 10–18% are medicinal in nature [Yadav M. & Misra S., 2012]. The MAP (medicinal aromatic plants) sub-sector is an integral part of natural resource management (NRM), contributing to economic growth, environmental protection and trade. The potential contribution of MAP can be substantial in capital-poor but resource-rich countries of South Asia if investment and efforts can be substantially increased in this sub-sector.

Tangible relationship of NTFP with the communities is nothing but, the things which should be harvested by forest dwellers. Like NTFPs Bamboo, fruits, honey, gums, resin, medicinal and aromatic plants etc. consider as a tangible NTFPs. community forest management also maintaining a good relationship with NTFP, through harvesting those above mentioned products. Intangible NTFPs is nothing but, the things which should not be harvested from the forest, like wild animals, timbers etc. Now days the forest dwellers are also maintaining a good relationship with intangible NTFPs by community forest management.

The main problem lies in unawareness of market prospects of NTFPs among these communities and tribal people due to which they never get the deserved value for their labour. This piece of work tries to suggest a framework which provides an interface between such communities of peoples and market so that they can avail the profits directly along with access to knowledge sharing platform which helps them in sharing and getting new ideas and suggestions, market prices, appropriate buyers etc. through a database design which manages all information for the same.

Few facts about NTFPs-

- NTFP contribute 10-40% of income of 50 million tribal households in India. In rural Madhya Pradesh, NTFP provide 40-63% of total annual income. (Tewari & Campbell, 1996).

- At global level, the estimated value of the market in herbal medicines alone is about USD 14 billion. (secretariat of the convention on biological diversity, 2001)
- At the local community level, NTFP can account for 35% (Cavendish, 1997) to as much 60% (Hedge et al. 1996) of household incomes.
- NWFP includes 3,000 species of plants, 250 essential oil yielding plants, 100 tans and dye yielding plants and 120 gums and resins yielding plants. (FAO, 2005)
- Being rich in natural resources India is one of the 12 mega biodiversity centres and holds about 50,000 plant species accounting for 7% world's flora. (Dayal et al., 1999)
- NTFP account for about 50% of the total forest revenue to the government and 70% of total forest based export, earning about half billion US Dollar in 1991.

1. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Edwards, D.M (1996) studied the trade of non timber forest product (NTFP) product in Nepal. The author discusses improvement in terms of increased production, direct marketing, and access to market information system, improved raw material and processing at local level by collective means of single institution. He advocates that single institution would lead to development of NTFP marketing and production.

Hegde, R et al (1996) studied livelihood of Soliga households of Biligiri range hills of Karnataka (India). They found that NTFP contributes half of the gross annual income even though the income that they generate from collection and selling of NTFP is much lesser as compared to other vocation.

Banana, A.Y (1998) identified the importance of organized information system so that farmers get actual returns on his plantation by determining appropriate price, market place and can promote merchandise. This in turn can lead

to sustainable harvest of NTFP at minimal loss of biodiversity.

Narendran et al (2001) evaluated the NTFP produce from Nilgiri biosphere reserve on ethnic diversity, social and economic aspects. They found that 50%-70% of the household of the region are dependent on forests. NTFP contribute up to 60% of the household income. They estimated mean annual income ranges between Rs. 134 to Rs.4955.

Gandhi,V.P Fangquan M (2002) describes the need of decision oriented marketing information system for forest and agro forest product in India. In his study based on primary survey on unsold stocks of forest and agro forest products in Madhya Pradesh identified the decision making needs of different players of forest products to answer the questions what and how much to buy?

Marshall E,Newton A.C and & Schreckenber K (2003) analysed the factor influencing success of NTFP and mentioned that market information as the key to successful commercialization of NTFPs.

Mahapatra A.K, Albers H.J, Robinson E.J.H (2005) studied the contribution of NTFP to cash income in dry deciduous forests of Orissa and Jharkhand. on the basis of data collected through the year, they found that the contribution of forest collect varies from 2% to 48% because of season, household income, proximity to resource, tradition ,skills, farm size, caste and climate.

Newton C.A.et al (2006) Studied 19 NTFP cases of Mexico and Bolivia, they analysed the causes of failure of commercialization of NTFP. They address the need of developing a probabilistic model based on livelihood framework which has five elements i.e. natural, physical, social, human and financial.

Rasul G, Karki M, Sah R.P (2008) studied the role of NTFP in income generation in India. They found that primary collector receive much lesser return because of constraints. They suggested to make NTFP really enhance the life of collector, The market structure, conditions for sustainable harvesting and management of NTFP must be improved.

Yadav M, Mishra S (2012) Studied the need of marketing information system and provide conceptual framework for medicinal and aromatic plants obtained mainly from forests. They discuss the need of marketing information system that integrate cultivator, forest department, and pharmaceutical companies. Thereby providing better returns to cultivator eliminating middlemen and the price fixing can be done by supply and demand mechanism.

PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

In this piece of work, we tried to expound an integrated framework using database concepts, which is available to tribal people and communities' dependant on forest resources through some sort of access point setup by a cooperative body which acts as an interface between NTFP collectors and market. These access points of such cooperative bodies can be established near market area of village or forest offices, where peoples can easily have its access. The requirement to setup such access points is to provide hands on training to a literate person from nearby village, with a setup of computer system and connectivity. In this way, such forest dwellers can easily earn a better livelihood by getting appropriate information on current prices, market situations, list of recognized buyers, and hence can avoid middle man, brokerage and black marketing. Subsequently, in the figure below we tried to structure a rough framework of how a NTFP collector gets access to outside scenario.

If observed at a sight, aforesaid concept seems to be an ordinary process, but in next level of the proposed work, emphasis is laid on functioning of cooperative body, which has a vital role in the story. In actual, the role of cooperative body includes maintaining inventory for the produce, details of NTFP collectors, details regarding customers, packaging item and supplier details etc. which is clearly depicted in the figure 2 below.

Figure 1: Rough idea of framework proposed

Functions like collection of NTFPs, data related to products, and collectors are being kept by a sub section of cooperative body named as Procurement unit, which is in connection with marketing and sales unit of cooperative body, which helps in fetching the facts related to current scenario of price and demands of NTFP produce. In addition to aforesaid functions, marketing and sales division possess customer

information database and order details along with packaging material and its supplier details. One more sub-section named warehouse unit which manages inventory database of acquired, available and supplied NTFPs. It also provides information to customers on NTFPs widely available in region and of immense use to the customers.

Figure 2: Detail functioning of Cooperative body

To illustrate another aspect of the framework suggested which expounds the interaction of databases for the functioning of cooperative body an entity relationship diagram is depicted below where all possible entities with their attributes and respective relationships are

shown. This paper does not claim the model to be ideal one and perfect in all aspects, but is a proposed framework to implement the idea of managing and regularizing the NTFPs and their collectors.

Figure 3: Entity relationship diagram of databases maintained by cooperative unit

In figure 3 representing entity relationship diagram, we supposed databases for NTFPs with attributes like pid (product id), ptype (product type i.e. nationalized NTFPs or Non nationalized NTFPs), price, quantity and best before date etc. which is being collected by NTFP collectors whose database is also to be maintained so as to eliminate middlemen and brokerage. These NTFP collectors also can have access to much information like current market price, trends, demands, and list of recognized buyers etc. which is accumulated at inventory database with respective attributes. In similar way database for customers and their orders is also needs to be maintained for proper fulfilment of demand. An optional database for packaging material is also represented which keeps track of packaging material and checks for minimum level and order the supplier if it falls short.

In an open market like of NTFPs especially in case of Non nationalized NTFPs, role of such integrated framework will be to regularize the demand and supply of products, ensure better economic returns to collectors and producers along with better quality to customers. Such models also helps in making a central database nationwide which helps Government in policy-making process with sustainable usage of resources.

CONCLUSIONS

The existing NTFP market in India is operating in a haphazard and unregulated manner. To regularize such markets for leading a win-win situation for customers and forest dwellers, collecting or cultivating such products, a framework for integrated database for NTFPs has been proposed from where NTFP collectors can access information like current price, market trend, and demands etc. and customers can get information on different NTFPs available. In this way role of middlemen can be eliminated who cheats both collectors and customers for their profit margins. Such framework will also help in fulfilling demand-supply gap along with proper monitoring and hold of such disseminated and unregulated market which ultimately results in social upsurge, poverty alleviation and development of the country.

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